

Supporting Information

CONSTRUCTIVE BY DESIGN? EVALUATING AN AI FEEDBACK COACH IN COLLABORATIVE LEARNING CONTEXTS

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1. Supplementary Methods

The design of peer feedback assignments

A 10-minute clip was provided to students with instructions and modelled examples on providing effective feedback, and highlighting the benefits for both feedback recipients and providers [1]. In class, lecturers discussed the role of the AFC (AI Feedback Coach) and its potential pitfalls, highlighting key practices such as writing comments first before reviewing feedback and disabling the AFC if perceived as unhelpful. Moreover, lecturers communicated clear quality expectations for the peer feedback and process [2]. Each feedback assignment included scaffolding with specific feedback questions that were derived from the rubrics used for grading [3]. A minimum of one comment per feedback criterion was enforced in the online feedback environment to ensure feedback on each important aspect of the video assignment. Students gave non-anonymous feedback on all criteria, with two days to complete each. A minimum number of comments was enforced in the online peer feedback environment to ensure feedback covered all assignment assessment criteria. The criteria for the video pitch assignment included non-verbal and verbal communication, message, video quality, and progress toward personal learning goals. For the peer feedback assignment on collaboration, the feedback criteria were derived from the CATME collaboration framework and included Contributing to the Team's Work, Interacting with Teammates, Keeping the Team on Track, Expecting Quality, and Having Relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities [4]. Since peer feedback was conducted in small groups, the feedback was given non-anonymously. Each student received at least two, but typically three, reviews of their performance on each assignment, which they were prompted to use actively in the different reflection assignments.

Quantitative analysis of feedback comments

Linguistic and sentiment analysis was performed using Python (v3.12.10) in Jupyter Notebook. Linguistic analysis was conducted using TextDescriptives (v2.8.4) on spaCy (v3.8.11) with the Dutch language model (nl_core_news_lg, v3.8.0). Sentiment analysis was performed using the multilingual BERT model (nlptown/bert-base-multilingual-uncased-sentiment) via Hugging Face Transformers (v4.37.0). Linguistic metrics and valence scores were compared between cohorts using R (v4.4.0) in RStudio (v2026.01.0). For univariate analysis, each metric was tested for normality with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Differences between control and intervention groups were examined using a two-sample t-test (normal distribution) or a Mann-Whitney U test (non-normal distribution). To adjust for multiple testing, a Bonferroni correction was employed. Significant differences were further explored by calculating effect sizes with the effectsize (v1.0.1) package, using Cohen's d (normal distribution) or Cliff's delta (non-normal distribution). For multivariate analysis of the text metrics, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and sparse Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis (sPLS-DA) were conducted using the FactoMineR (v2.12), factoextra (v1.0.7), and mixOmics (v6.30.0) packages. PCA assessed unsupervised separation between control and intervention cohorts, while sPLS-DA identified the variables most contributing to their differences.

2. Supplementary Figures

Figure S1 A) Self-reported frequency of AFC feedback use (n=72) B) Self-reported adjustments to own peer feedback based on AFC feedback (n=66)

Figure S2: Responses to the question: "Did you turn off the AI coach at any point in time?" (n=72).

Figure S3: Principal component analysis of the linguistic metrics. PC1 (19.1%) and PC2 (15.6%) show complete overlap, indicating no structural differences between the control and intervention group.

Figure S4: Sparse Partial Least Squares Discriminant Analysis of the linguistic metrics. Although Component 1 (18.4% X-variance) and Component 2 (6.8% X-variance) capture some variation, the two groups overlap almost entirely, suggesting no structural differences between the control and intervention groups, but rather specific local differences.

Figure S5: Results of manual sentiment coding of all student responses ($n=56$) to the survey question “How did you experience being coached by the AI feedback coach?”

Figure S6: Example of inconsistent automated feedback on student feedback comments generated by the AFC (AI feedback coach). A. Shows feedback that is considered constructive by the feedback coach, whereas B. shows comparable feedback, which is regarded as “not constructive”.

3. Supplementary Tables

Table S1: List of all survey items distributed to students via Qualtrics at the end of the course, with the qualitative answer option range (scale range), the number of answer options (Likert scale) on the literature an item is based on.

#	Item	Scale range	Likert scale	Based on
1	What is your gender	-	-	-
2	In what year did you start your studies in Pharmaceutical Sciences?	-	-	-
3	How would you describe your experience with giving peer feedback before you started this project?	No expertise - Expert	5	-
4	I reflect on the quality of my own work and use my reflection as a source of information to improve my work.	Never-Always	6	-
5	I carefully consider comments about my work before deciding if I will use them or not.	Never-Always	6	[5]
6	When deciding what to do with comments, I consider the credibility of their sources.	Never-Always	6	[5]
7	I use comments on my work to refine my understanding of what good quality work looks like.	Never-Always	6	[5]
8	When I receive comments from others, I use them to improve what I'm working on at the time.	Never-Always	6	[5]
9	When commenting on the work of others, I provide constructive criticism.	Never-Always	6	[5]
10	I try to be very clear when providing feedback comments to others.	Never-Always	6	[5]
11	I am open to reasonable criticism about my work.	Never-Always	6	[5]
12	I make use of critical comments even if they are difficult to receive.	Never-Always	6	[5]
13	How often have you used the AI coach (approximately) to get feedback on the peer feedback you wrote?	1-4, 5-9, 10-20, 21 or more, Always	-	-
14	Did you turn off the AI coach at any point in time?	No, Yes directly, Yes after a while, Yes with 2 nd assignment, Other	-	-
15	Through the use of the AI coach in this course, I feel that I provided more constructive feedback to my fellow students.	Disagree-Agree	7	-
16	I considered the feedback I received from the AFC justified.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
17	I considered the feedback I received from the AFC useful.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
18	I considered the feedback I received from the AFC helpful.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
19	The feedback I received from the AFC provided me with a lot of support.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
20	I accepted the feedback I received from the AFC.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
21	I disputed the feedback I received from the AFC.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
22	After receiving feedback from the AFC, I was willing to improve my peer feedback.	Disagree-Agree	7	[6]
23	Thanks to the AFC, I am more confident that the peer feedback I give to other students is of good quality.	Disagree-Agree	7	[7]
24	Thanks to the AFC, I am more confident that the peer feedback I give to other students helps them improve their work.	Disagree-Agree	7	[7]
25	What type(s) of adjustments did you make to your peer feedback based on the AI feedback? Please note: multiple answers are possible!	Disagree-Agree	7	-
26	I would use the AI coach more often in the future if it were made available.	Disagree-Agree	7	-
27	How did you experience being coached by the AI feedback coach?	Open		-
28	Do you have (other) tips for the improvement of the (technical) implementation of the AI feedback coach?	Open		-
29	You indicated that you did not use the AI coach in the peer feedback assignments where it was available. Briefly explain why not.	Open		-

Table S2: Descriptive statistics of selected survey items related to the Feedback Literacy Behavior Scale (FLBS) on a 6-point Likert-scale (N=72) [5]. The percentages are calculated by grouping the respective answers. The center of the scale is 3.5.

Item	Mean	SD	Never	% Seldom / Sometimes	% Regularly / Often	% Always
I reflect on the quality of my own work and use my reflection as a source of information to improve my work.	4.2	0.8	0.0	16.7	77.8	5.6
I carefully consider comments about my work before deciding if I will use them or not.	4.8	0.8	0.0	5.6	80.6	13.9
When deciding what to do with comments, I consider the credibility of their sources.	4.0	1.3	1.4	36.1	50.0	12.5
I use comments on my work to refine my understanding of what good quality work looks like.	4.4	1.0	1.4	11.1	75.0	12.5
When I receive comments from others, I use them to improve what I'm working on at the time.	4.6	0.8	0.0	9.7	80.6	9.7
When commenting on the work of others, I provide constructive criticism.	4.4	0.9	0.0	12.5	80.6	6.9
I try to be very clear when providing feedback comments to others.	4.9	0.8	0.0	4.2	69.4	26.4
I am open to reasonable criticism about my work.	5.2	0.8	0.0	1.4	62.5	36.1
I make use of critical comments even if they are difficult to receive.	4.6	1.0	0.0	12.5	66.7	20.8

Table S3: Results of the univariate analysis of linguistic measures from the TextDescriptives package. Shown are the normality (normal means that the metric for both the control and the intervention group showed normal distribution), the center metric (mean for normally distributed, median for non-normally distributed) and the adjusted P-value after Bonferroni correction. N/A indicates that for the control and/or intervention group all values were identical and thus statistics could not be calculated.

Linguistic metric	Normality	Center 2024	Center 2025	Adjusted P-value
Document Size & Basic Counts				
Number of tokens (words or word-like units)	not-normal	227.50	211.50	1.000
Number of sentences	not-normal	20.00	17.00	0.401
Document length (characters or tokens)	not-normal	252.50	235.50	1.000
Number of characters in the text	not-normal	1104.50	1024.00	1.000
Number of stop words	not-normal	122.00	115.50	1.000
Lexical Composition & Diversity				
Number of unique tokens	not-normal	116.00	115.50	1.000
Ratio of alphabetic characters to total characters	not-normal	0.88	0.88	1.000
Out-of-vocabulary token ratio	not-normal	0.03	0.03	1.000
Proportion of unique tokens (type-token ratio)	not-normal	0.51	0.55	0.002
Mean token length (in characters)	not-normal	4.69	4.80	0.011
Median token length	not-normal	4.00	4.00	1.000
Standard deviation of token lengths	not-normal	3.03	3.09	1.000
Mean number of characters per word	not-normal	4.29	4.45	0.001
Mean number of syllables per token	not-normal	1.58	1.61	0.232

Median number of syllables per token	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Standard deviation of syllables per token	not-normal	0.96	0.99	1.000
Ratio of symbols (such as #) to words	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Readability & Grade-Level Metric				
Flesch Reading Ease score	not-normal	60.93	58.02	0.036
Automated Readability Index (ARI)	normal	6.90	7.63	0.017
Coleman–Liau Readability Index	not-normal	9.17	10.10	0.001
Flesch–Kincaid Grade Level	not-normal	7.66	8.33	0.095
Gunning Fog Index	not-normal	10.93	11.45	0.180
LIX Readability Score	not-normal	35.13	37.68	0.006
RIX Readability Index	not-normal	2.72	3.06	0.029
SMOG Readability Index	not-normal	10.69	11.10	0.124
Sentence Length & Complexity				
Mean sentence length (in tokens)	not-normal	12.00	12.25	1.000
Median sentence length	not-normal	11.50	12.00	1.000
Standard deviation of sentence length	not-normal	7.42	7.30	1.000
Syntactic Structure (Dependency-based)				
Mean syntactic dependency distance	not-normal	2.47	2.50	1.000
Standard deviation of syntactic dependency distance	normal	1.21	1.18	1.000
Mean proportion of adjacent dependency relations	normal	0.35	0.34	1.000
Standard deviation of adjacent dependency relation proportion	not-normal	0.14	0.13	1.000
Coherence				
First-order coherence (adjacent sentence similarity)	not-normal	0.51	0.51	1.000
Second-order coherence (similarity across sentence pairs separated by one sentence)	not-normal	0.52	0.51	1.000
Repetition & Redundancy				
Fraction of characters in duplicate lines	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate 5-grams	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate 6-grams	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate 7-grams	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate 8-grams	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate 9-grams	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate 10-grams	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Fraction of characters in duplicate paragraphs	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Character fraction of the top 2-gram	not-normal	0.01	0.01	0.350
Character fraction of the top 3-gram	not-normal	0.01	0.01	1.000
Character fraction of the top 4-gram	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Part-of-Speech Distribution				
Proportion of adjectives	not-normal	0.10	0.10	1.000
Proportion of adpositions (prepositions/postpositions)	normal	0.11	0.11	1.000
Proportion of adverbs	normal	0.09	0.09	1.000

Proportion of auxiliary verbs	not-normal	0.06	0.06	1.000
Proportion of coordinating conjunctions	not-normal	0.03	0.03	1.000
Proportion of determiners	normal	0.08	0.08	1.000
Proportion of interjections	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Proportion of nouns	normal	0.15	0.16	1.000
Proportion of numerals	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Proportion of particles	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Proportion of pronouns	not-normal	0.10	0.10	1.000
Proportion of proper nouns	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Proportion of punctuation tokens	not-normal	0.10	0.10	1.000
Proportion of subordinating conjunctions	not-normal	0.02	0.02	0.270
Proportion of symbols	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Proportion of verbs	normal	0.12	0.12	1.000
Proportion of miscellaneous/other POS tags	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Formatting				
Proportion of text that is bullet points	not-normal	0.00	0.00	1.000
Proportion of ellipses (...) in the text	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table S4: Effect size analysis of linguistic measures. Center metric is either the median for non-normally distributed data or the mean for normally distributed data. Adjusted P-value is the P-value after Bonferroni correction for multiple testing. Positive effect sizes indicate higher scores for the control cohort (without AFC), whereas negative effect sizes indicate higher scores for the intervention cohort with AFC. All metrics are analyzed using Cliff's delta, except Automated Readability Index, which is analyzed using Cohen's d (as the data was normally distributed). Cliff's delta was interpreted following Romano et al. 2006, in which $|\delta| < 0.147$ is negligible effect, $0.147 \leq |\delta| < 0.33$ is small effect, $0.33 \leq |\delta| < 0.474$ is medium effect and $|\delta| \geq 0.474$ is large effect [8]. Cohen's d was interpreted following Cohen (1988), in which 0.2 = small effect, 0.5 = medium effect and 0.8 = large effect [9].

Linguistic metric	Explanation	Center 2024	Center 2025	Adjusted P-value	Effect size	Qualitative effect size
Flesch Reading Ease score	How easy is a text to read	60.93	58.02	0.036	0.20	Small
Automated Readability Index (ARI)	Grade level needed to understand text	6.90	7.63	0.017	-0.38	Small to medium
Coleman-Liau Readability Index	Reading grade level	9.17	10.10	0.001	-0.26	Small
LIX Readability Score	Readability index	35.13	37.68	0.006	-0.23	Small
RIX Readability Index	Readability index, focus on long words	2.72	3.06	0.029	-0.21	Small
Mean Word length	Number of characters per word	4.29	4.45	0.001	-0.26	Small
Proportion of unique tokens	Lexical diversity	0.51	0.55	0.002	-0.25	Small

Mean token length	Number of characters per token	4.69	4.80	0.011	-0.22	Small
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4. Limitations

A few limitations of the current study should be reported. Hardly any differences in feedback characteristics were observed between intervention and control cohorts. Three possible explanations could have caused this, offsetting any potential benefits of the AFC. First, baseline feedback quality was already relatively high for both cohorts, potentially due to explicit feedback instruction, rubric-based prompts, and their prior feedback experience, which can already mitigate common feedback quality issues [10]. Alternatively, feedback on skills might be perceived as more personal than feedback on writing products, potentially stimulating students to carefully construct their feedback irrespective of the AFC. Alternatively, the students might already feel comfortable giving feedback on presentation skills, which requires less expertise (content knowledge) than feedback on written products related to the course material. Both options might suggest that, in this context, additional coaching may yield only limited observable gains. Consequently, there might have been differences in feedback quality due to the AFC in cohorts with less experience in peer feedback or in cohorts where peer feedback artifacts require greater content knowledge to provide effective feedback. A third explanation is that the experimental and intervention groups were not from the same cohort. There may be subtle differences between the two cohorts that could explain the significant variation in feedback complexity, unrelated to the AFC. Another limitation is that all data were analyzed at the cohort level, with no direct link between the student perception data and the objective feedback analysis due to anonymity. It might be that zooming in on groups with specific AFC usage patterns or feedback literacy traits reveals differences in feedback quality. Additionally, for the quality comparison of the feedback, one important feedback dimension was not considered: whether the praise or suggestions students provided in peer feedback were valid. More in-depth analysis would be needed to answer the question whether the AFC would have an effect on feedback validity or correctness. Although similar results have been found in a comparable study by Hansen and colleagues [2], our study was a case study with relatively low student numbers and a specific academic context, which might have influenced the generalizability of our results.

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